

Trends in in-situ aerosol optical properties across the globe

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Atmospheric aerosol particles impact climate directly by interacting with solar radiation (i.e., by scattering and absorbing light) and indirectly by serving as cloud condensation nuclei. Aerosol particles can also affect air quality, resulting in health and safety issues. Investigating aerosol trends is useful for understanding the effectiveness of regulations to control anthropogenic emissions as well as identifying the impacts of evolving natural emissions (e.g., wildfires, dust, biogenics). Because aerosol particles are short-lived atmospheric species, the distribution of aerosol around the globe is inhomogeneous. This leads to regional effects of aerosols which can influence the hydrologic cycle (e.g., Persad and Caldeira, 2018; Persad, 2023). Thus, it is important to look at trends at local and regional scales as well as in the global context.

It can be challenging to detect change. Trends can be obscured by inconsistencies and breakpoints in the time series. This highlights the need to have detailed metadata for the observations. Necessary metadata includes documentation on instrument and system changes as well as operational and data processing changes. While it is good practice to have overlapping observations when making measurement changes, that isn't always possible due to limitations in funding, physical space or time and logistics. It is often possible to homogenize time series when overlapping observations are available. To ensure the accurate trend analysis, each time series will be visually inspected to identify potential issues (shifts, discontinuities, etc). Additionally, two automated techniques (the Pettitt test and the Standard Normal Homogeneity Test (SNHT)) will be used to identify breakpoints and anomalies in the time series (Collaud Coen, in prep).

This work is built on previous work investigating trends and variability in atmospheric aerosol (Collaud Coen et al., 2020a; Laj et al., 2020; Mortier et al., 2020; Gliß et al., 2021; Asmi et al., 2013; Collaud Coen et al., 2013). Collaud Coen et al. (2020a) reported trends in measured aerosol scattering and absorption coefficients and in derived aerosol properties (single scattering albedo, back-scattering fraction and scattering Ångström exponent) at 52 sites. Here we extend the analysis of Collaud Coen et al. (2020a) investigating trends in in-situ aerosol optical properties ending in the time period 2016-2018 to time series with end dates 2023-2025 time frame. The additional years since the previous study means there are now more sites with observational time series long enough for trend analysis.

Collaud Coen et al. (2020a) applied the non-parametric seasonal Mann–Kendall statistical test associated with several pre-whitening methods and with Sen's slope was used as the main trend analysis method (see Collaud Coen et al. 2020b for details). In this new study, quantile regression trends will also be determined. Quantile regression trends (Koenker and Hallet, 2001) provide information on how

parameters are changing at the extremes, which can then be attributed to increases in exceptional events like wildfires or dust storms (e.g., Boedicker et al., 2026).

The focus is primarily on trends at background (non-urban) sites. A primary source of data are those submitted to the World Data Centre for Aerosols archive EBAS which hosts data from various networks such as ACTRIS (Laj et al., 2024) and NFAN (Andrews et al., 2019) as well as some independent sites. To increase spatial coverage beyond what is available in EBAS, other networks and observatories have been contacted, expanding the analysis to approximately 100 sites (Figure 1). The bulk of the measurements locations are still in Europe and North America, but for the first time we hope to include multiple sites from Africa and South America and as well as more locations in Asia.

This trend analysis is intended to answer the following questions:

1. Is statistical breakpoint detection useful for the detection of breakpoints in atmospheric aerosol time series?
2. Have aerosol loading related trends continued to decrease as previously observed (Collaud Coen et al., 2020a)?
3. How have derived property trends evolved?
4. Are there trends in the extremes and can those trends be related to exceptional events?

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